

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

FLAGSHIP PROJECT GRIP

SPOKE N 2 – Title GREEN TECHNOLOGIES AND SUSTAINABLE INDUSTRIES

DELIVERABLE D1.2

REPORTING PERIOD	
Period covered:	from [01/09/2023] to [31/10/2024]
Periodic report date and version:	[31/10/2024]
Task 1.2 Leader	Elio Padoan (UNITO)
D1.2 Responsible	Giovanna Antonella Dino (UNITO)

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

A) Main objectives achieved

- The main objectives of this RM are the Collection of data, processing technologies and waste characterization.
- The primary objective of this deliverable (D 1.2) was the characterization of the wastes selected during the first reporting period (and reported in D1.1) and the development of the processes and the technologies selected to treat the organic or mineral wastes. After

the development of the technologies, main goal of this task was the characterization of the new products and byproducts.

- During the 14 months of task 1.2 all the partners collected data on the wastes and established practices for the efficient and sustainable management of these waste streams.
- The main results of the task, reported in the deliverable are:
 - the production of a database reporting the characteristics of the investigated mineral and organic waste and (recycled) products obtained after treatment activities;
 - the production of a simple operative manual to populate and fill the database.

Table - List of Deliverables (M1: January 2023)

NUM	OUTPUTS/DELIVERABLE NAME	TYPE*	SHORT DESCRIPTION	LEAD PARTICIPANT	DISSEMINATION LEVEL**	DUEDATE
D1.1	Collection of data, processing technologies	R	A database and a report on collected information (production, characteristics, and localisation data, together with representative processing technologies).	POLITO	PU	M9
D1.2	Characterization of waste and new products from Mineral and bio-organic waste.	DB	A database reporting the characteristics of the investigated mineral and organic waste and (recycled) products obtained after treatment activities (described in T1.3) will be delivered. Together with it, an operative manual to populate and fill the database will be also produced.	UNITO	PU	M22
D1.3	Treatment and processing activities for mineral and bio-organic waste	R	A report on the investigated treatment activities (methodologies, procedures, limits, etc.) will be produced.	UNITO	PU	M24
D1.4	Pilot Sites Recycled Products Application	R	Pilot sites to test and validate the proposed technologies will be assessed	UNITO	PU	M32

Table - List of Project Milestones

MILESTONE NUMBER	MILESTONE NAME	RELATED WORK MODULES	DUE DATE (MONTH)	MEANS OF VERIFICATION
MS1.1	Treatment Activities for EQW, CDW, EW	1	12	Planning and authorisation delivered
MS1.2	Data collection and processing of EQW, CDW, EW, CW	1	12	Collection of data and processing info for LCA within the due date (LCA linked to RM6)
MS1.3	Pilot Sites testing activities	1	18	Planning and authorisation delivered
MS1.4	Recycled Products Application (from MW/OBW)	1	24	Planning and authorisation delivered

A) EXPLANATION OF THE WORK CARRIED OUT AND OVERVIEW OF THE PROGRESS

Research Module n. 1	Start month: 1	End month: 32
Title: Circular waste, processing of Mineral and Organic Biowaste		
Location in Mezzogiorno: N		
Leader:	UNITO	
Partners involved:	POLITO	UPO
Type of action	Industrial Research	
Effort in person/months	160,5	

Output and results:

During the activities of task 1.2, all the seven working groups defined in the previous task (Task1.1) were working on the development of protocols to produce the new products. Moreover, the investigated wastes and products were characterized according to best practices and innovations.

Here is a short list of the processes that have been identified and the wastes that have been characterized for each research team. The full list and characterization are in the following syllabus database.

Research Team A

- Technosols for environmental rehabilitation: construction and demolition waste (fine fractions) and soil from excavation activities have been studied together with compost and digestates from urban bio-wastes. The products of the processes (regenerated soils for green infrastructures) were also characterized.
- Technosols for new horse footing areas: construction and demolition waste (both fine and coarse fractions - recycled aggregates) and wastes from extractive waste facilities in Piedmont and Tuscany were studied to evaluate particle size distribution and other physical and chemical characteristics (e.g. trace elements and minerals present).
- Circular mortars: investigated wastes were marble powder, rice husk, hemp fibers and cork. Technical, mineralogical, chemical tests on different formulations are in progress.
- Enforced embankments soils for civil and infrastructure applications: after a first characterization stage at laboratory level of construction and demolition waste and soil from

excavation activities, the application and testing at pilot sites are in progress.

Research Team B

The team investigated carbonatic and dolomitic rock waste material from quarries of different kinds, including ornamental stones all over Italy with petrographic, mineralogical, and geotechnical techniques according to UE standards.

Research Team C

The studied wastes were fired ceramic scraps (FCS) and bottom ashes from municipal solid waste incineration for their reuse in ceramic production in the partial replacement of feldspar. Wastes were investigated technologically and mineralogically through different techniques. Further investigations are in progress also in the newly produced ceramic tiles with wastes in the formulation.

Research Team D

Investigated waste was the organic fraction of municipal solid waste (OFMSW) and different anaerobic digestates produced with physical and enzymatic pretreatments. The pretreatments were applied on the substrate, alone or in combination, before performing anaerobic digestion for 24 days. The digestates are to be fully characterized and their liquid fraction will be utilized as substrate for struvite precipitation.

Research Team E

The team focuses on the equine stable bedding waste. The three most commonly used equine bedding wastes (dung and urine mixed with rice husks, straw and sawdust) were analyzed and tested for optimizing the conversion procedures into biochar and activated carbon for gas sorption, tuning the pores size and the surface area to improve the performance.

Research Team F

The team focuses agro-industrial wastes and their use in livestock and on bio-based valorization using combined sustainable processing for the production of high value functional ingredients for food and nutraceuticals.

Research Team G.

The research team focuses on the reuse of cereal and food waste for energy storage. Fungal species able to colonize organic wastes with different chemical characteristics (cereal wastes, bean pods) have been selected and the obtained processed materials have been subjected to pyrolysis and tested as hydrogen storage materials. All materials have been characterized using chemical, spectroscopical and physical techniques.

[Database Syllabus \(D1.2\)](#)

A database was developed to collect information about the characteristics of the mineral and organic wastes previously selected as starting materials, as well as the products achieved after the application

of the investigated processes.

The database is organized as follows:

Investigated waste: the wastes utilized as starting materials for the processes are listed by each research team, specifying their origin and usual destination sector.

Methodologies used to investigate the waste characteristics: in this entry, the techniques applied to analyze the original wastes are briefly summarized.

Characteristics of the investigated waste: the results of the waste analyses are outlined. Data about both chemical and physical features are presented.

Treatments used to obtain the new products: the processes utilized to convert the original wastes into the desired products are mentioned, highlighting the limitations of the treatment and the scale at which they were tested.

The new products: the products achieved from the developed processes are described, together with their destination sector.

Methodologies used to investigate the new products: analogously to what was done for the original wastes, the database lists the methods involved in the products analyses.

Characteristics of the new products: the chemical and physical features of the new products that have already been characterized are listed in this entry. This part of the database will be concluded in the coming months.

Energetical characteristics of the process (LCA): the research teams are collecting information that will be useful to perform the life cycle assessment by the colleagues in RM6. These data will be implemented in the next months.

The database is actually in progress and it will be updated until the end of Task 1.3 .

The database can be found at the following [link](#)